

Bioengineered Bile Duct: Up-to-date on 2018

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Aim

Development of the physiologically relevant tissue-engineered graft for repair of bile duct injuries (Dyuzheva et al., 2016).

Highlights

- We define to construct a design of physiologically relevant multilayered tube (Klabukov et al., 2017) consisting of three synthetic polymers layers and two types of cells: bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSCs) and cholangiocytes.
- All polymers were tested for biocompatibility with the use of two cell lines: fibroblasts 3T3 and epitheliocytes MCF7 cells (Lyundup et al., 2016).
- The inner layer was formed with bile duct epitheliocytes and PCL modified by EGF during an electrospinning fabrication, which allows to stimulate an epithelial cells proliferation (Tenchurin et al., 2017).
- The medium layer was formed by PCL thin film. The outer layer of the tube included a copolymer PCL/PLGA (70:30) with seeded MSCs and cholangiocytes. It was proposed an approach for designing of synthetic scaffold based on degradation and biomechanical behaviour of materials (Tenchurin et al., 2018).
- The PCL fiber layer modified with VEGF165 plasmid (Neovascugen™) increase of local angiogenesis on 46% after subcutaneous implantation in rats (Klabukov et al., 2018).

Conclusions

Designed scaffold showed no cytotoxicity, both BM-MSCs and cholangiocytes migrated into the depth of fibrous material. The constructs was biodegradable in various model mediums: deionized water, phosphate buffer, bile, full culture medium. The next step is pre-clinical trials on rabbits and minipigs for assessment of implantation safety and efficacy. We suppose that this tubular multilayered tissue-engineered construct will be capable to integration in native tissues after implantation and may be used to injured bile duct reparation.

References

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Acknowledgments

Supported by Ministry of Education and Science of Russian Federation (agreement no. 14.604.21.0133 [RFMEFI60414X0133], 2014-2018).